

enviro

chem

3 INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL CHEMISTRY CONGRESS

01-04 November 2021

Kemer ANTALYA

ABSTRACTS AND PROCEEDINGS E-BOOK

FOREWORD

3rd International Environmental Chemistry (EnviroChem) Congress

We are proud to organize our third congress by the [Turkish Chemists Society](#) under the title of Environmental Chemistry. As will be remembered, we organized our first congress with the title of 1st Eurasian Environmental Chemistry Congress in 2018 and our second congress with the title of 2nd International Environmental Chemistry Congress in 2019. This year, the third of our congress was held under the title of [3rd International Environmental Chemistry Congress \(EnviroChem\)](#).

This congress was organised by Erciyes University, Karadeniz Technical University and Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University. The main purpose of this congress was to establish a warm environment to share cutting-edge information on developments in all areas of environmental chemistry research. The congress aims to bring together researchers from the entire spectrum of the multi-disciplinary fields of environmental chemistry and establish effective means of communication between them. This year we had participants from Algeria, Azerbaijan, France, Germany, Iran, Kosovo, Morocco, Russia, Nigeria, Palestinian, Pakistan, Tatarstan, Turkey, Tunisia, Ukraine, UK and USA. Eight invited speakers and more than 120 researchers presented their research work as oral/poster presentations.

On behalf of the organizing committee, we would like to thank you all for joining us and contributing to the success of the EnviroChem 2021. As an integral and significant part of this conference, your attendance added tremendous value. We also greatly acknowledge Ness İletişim, SEM, Terra, Redoks, ChromaScience and Naz Laboratuvar for their very generous sponsorships and supports in the organisation of 3rd International Environmental Chemistry Congress (EnviroChem).

Last but not the least we greatly appreciate the contributions of the local Organizing Committee who have spent their energy on the success of this congress. We want to thank Mirage Park Resort (Göynük, Kemer, Antalya/Turkey) for their excellent services.

Best wishes.

Prof. Mustafa SOYLAK (Chair)
Assoc. Prof. Ali ALKAN (Co-Chair)
Assoc. Prof. Ahmet DEMIRAK (Co-Chair)

November 2021

COMMITTEES

Congress Chair

Prof. Mustafa SOYLAK Erciyes University, TURKEY

Congress Co-Chairs

Assoc. Prof. Ali ALKAN Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY

Assoc. Prof. Ahmet DEMİRAK Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University, TURKEY

Congress Secretary

Prof. Volkan Numan BULUT Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY

Advisory Board

Prof. Ahmet Cemal SAYDAM Hacettepe University, TURKEY

Prof. Şeref GÜÇER Uludağ University, TURKEY

Prof. Reşat APAK İstanbul University, TURKEY

Prof. Mehmet TÜFEKÇİ Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY

Prof. Günay KOCASOY Boğaziçi University, TURKEY

Scientific Committee

Prof. Bülent KESKİNLER Gebze Technical University, TURKEY

Prof. Irina KARADJOVA Sofia University, BULGARIA

Prof. Rashid AHMAD University of Malakand, PAKISTAN

Prof. Emilio BENFENATI The Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research, ITALY

Prof. Mustafa TÜZEN Gaziosmanpaşa University, TURKEY

Prof. Alla OUDALOVA National Research Nuclear University, RUSSIA

Prof. Oktay ÖZKAN Erciyes University, TURKEY

Prof. Rashid SALGHI National School of Applied Science, MOROCCO

Prof. Gürdal TUNCEL Middle East Technical University, TURKEY

Prof. Gerasimos LYBERATOS National Technical University of Athens, GREECE

Prof. Sezgin BAKIRDERE Yıldız Technical University, TURKEY

Prof. Ryszard LOBINSKI Equipe de Chimie Analytique Bio-Inorganique CNRS, FRANCE

Assoc. Prof. Gábor MAASZ Pannonia University, HUNGARY

Prof. Antony C. CALOKERINOS National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, GREECE

Prof. Trajce STAFILOV SS Cyril Meth University, MACEDONIA

Prof. Cengiz KAVAKLI Hacettepe University, TURKEY

Prof. Yasemin ÖZTEKİN Selçuk University, TURKEY

Prof. Yücel KADIOĞLU Atatürk University, TURKEY

Prof. Uğur TAMER Gazi University, TURKEY

Prof. Pınar AKKAŞ KAVAKLI Hacettepe University, TURKEY

Prof. Esra YEL Konya Technical University, TURKEY

Prof. Bahattin YALÇIN Marmara University, TURKEY

Prof. Michael O. ANGELIDIS University of the Aegean, GREECE

Prof. Mustafa ERSÖZ Selçuk University, TURKEY

Prof. Gülay BAYRAMOĞLU Gazi University, TURKEY

Prof. Süreyya MERİÇ PAGANO Namık Kemal University, TURKEY

Prof. Levgenii GERASIMOV National University of Water and Environmental Engineering, UKRAINE

Prof. Zeynep CEYLAN Atatürk University, TURKEY

Assoc. Prof. Gülay ERTAŞ Middle East Technical University, TURKEY

Assoc. Prof. Elmina GADIROVA	Baku State University, AZERBAIJAN
Assoc. Prof. Mustafa YÜCEL	Middle East Technical University, TURKEY
Assoc. Prof. Ali SUNGUR	Çanakkale 18 Mart University, TURKEY
Assoc. Prof. Ezel BOYACI	Middle East Technical University, TURKEY
Assoc. Prof. İlknur D. TEMUGE	Hacettepe University, TURKEY
Assoc. Prof. H. Aytekin ERGÜL	Kocaeli University, TURKEY
Assoc. Prof. Erkan YILMAZ	Erciyes University, TURKEY
Assoc. Prof. Abolfazl NAJI	Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research, GERMANY
Assist. Prof. Usama ALSHANA	Near East University, Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC)
Dr. Yatsiuk MYKHAİLO	Institute of Water Problems and Land Reclamation, UKRAINE

Organizing Committee

Prof. Ali GÜNDOĞDU	Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY
Prof. Nigar ALKAN	Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY
Prof. Mykhaylo ROMASHCHENKO	Institute of Water Problems and Land Reclamation, UKRAINE
Assist. Prof. Barbaros DİNÇER	Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, TURKEY
Assist. Prof. Pınar SEVİM ELİBOL	Düzce University, TURKEY
Assist. Prof. Umar KHAN DURRANI	Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY
Assoc. Prof. Mariia NESTERKINA	Odessa National Polytechnic University, UKRAINE
Dr. Melek KOÇ KEŞİR	Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY
Dr. Zeliha ERBAŞ	Yozgat Bozok University, TURKEY
Dr. Iskander GILMANSHIN	Kazan Federal University, Kazan, RUSSIA
Chemist, Nilüfer KUTUROĞLU	Ministry of Environment and Urbanization, TURKEY
MSc. Berrin ÖZKILIÇ	Karadeniz Technical University, TURKEY
Furkan UZCAN	Erciyes University, TURKEY
Seda DUMAN	Erciyes University, TURKEY
Özgür ÖZALP	Erciyes University, TURKEY
Ümit Güven ULUSOY	ASKI, TURKEY
Feyza YALÇIN	Haliç Çevre Laboratuvarı, TURKEY

Steering Committee

Assoc. Prof. Ali ALKAN	Karadeniz Technical University, On Behalf of Turkish Chemist Society
Assoc. Prof. Ahmet DEMİRAK	Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University
Prof. Münevver SÖKMEN	Konya Food and Agriculture University (1. EnviroChem Congress Chair)
Prof. Bekir SALİH	Hacettepe University (2. EnviroChem Congress Chair)

Congress Owner (On Behalf of Turkish Chemist Society)

Chemist İkrâm CENGİZ	Head of Turkish Chemist Society
----------------------	---------------------------------

OP – 41

The Effect of Climate Change on the Fishing Ports in the Eastern Black Sea

Kadir Seyhan¹, Koray Özşeker², Umar Khan Durrani², Şebnem Atasaral¹, Yahya Terzi¹

¹Karadeniz Technical University Faculty of Marine Sciences, Trabzon, Turkey

²Institute of Marine Sciences and Technology, Karadeniz Technical University, Trabzon, Turkey
seyhan@ktu.edu.tr

The total landing of the Turkish marine fishes is about as reported 375 thousand tonnes in 2019, of which 70% is anchovy. The Turkish Black Sea fisheries are highly dependent on these small pelagic fish stocks. Understanding the biology and behavior of this species as well as the factors affecting the marine environment and hence the management of living resources are crucial for sustainable fisheries. This is also essential to boost the economic income without interrupting the blue growth. The Eastern Black Sea fish landing ports get around 50% of the total land, and most of this (~40%) is landed only at three, Yozgat (Trabzon), Fındıklı (Rize), and Hopa (Artvin). However, due to an increase in the rainfall during the last two decades, notably during the last couple of years, loading the ports have increased, and that needs to be reformulated for the fishing, and necessary measures should be taken if needed, and hence blue growth in the fishing community is not to be interrupted. Therefore, the core action here is to collect and study the relevant hydrological and meteorological observations data, topographic and bathymetric maps, and other materials to process and classify the obtained data on geomorphological changes and Port Modelling.

We will give an example to show how sediment movement is affecting the fishing ports and what advice can be provided for the ports management authorities.